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Part-time Engineering Master Programmes: Implementing Real-life Engineering Problems as a Means of Learning.

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For more than two decades, University Aalborg has enrolled learners into their part-time engineering Master's programmes. These programmes are designed for employed learners who work full-time in the industry and who want to keep their job while they study on a Master's programme. Aalborg University's pedagogical approach is solely based on problem-based learning, which means that learners are, to a large extent, implementing real-life engineering problems as a means of learning. This paper will investigate what types of problem formations the learners are able to identify from their working-life, which is also aligned with the requirements of the part-time master's study programme.

Conference Key Areas: continuing engineering education and lifelong learning

Keywords: continuing engineering education, problem based learning, problem formations

INTRODUCTION

For more than two decades, University Aalborg have enrolled students into its part-time engineering master's programmes. These programmes are designed for employed learners who work full-time in the industry and who wish to keep their job while they study on a Master's program. Consequently, the courses and seminars are mainly given in the evening and during weekends.

The part-time Master's should not be mistaken for the traditional Master's of Science (MSc) programmes, which according to Bologna is two years of study (120 ECTS) following a Bachelor's degree. The part-time Master's programmes are specially prepared to meet the needs of employed learners who lack knowledge, skills and competence within exact identified areas (subjects). The curriculums are carefully designed to be attractive and exciting for the engineers and they provide an opportunity to work with authentic problems from the learner's professional life. Thus, the Master's programmes are 60 ECTS, of which at least 30 ECTS of the programme content is project-work and the 30 ECTS are subject courses or seminars. The

extensive amount of resources dedicated to project work allows the learners to identify, analyse and solve real-life engineering problems in-depth.

This paper will investigate what types of problem formation the learners are able to identify from their working life, which also is aligned with the requirements of the part-time Master's study programme.

1 THE MASTER'S PROGRAMMES

The Master's programmes at Aalborg University, to a large extent, implement real-life engineering problems as means of learning. This concept of 'posing problems' as a means of learning began in the 1960s when Paulo Freire described '*the banking concept of education*', which is still prevalent as '*education becomes an act of depositing, in which the students [learners] are the depositories and the teacher is the depositor*' (Freire, 2009 p. 72). This educational approach, with the teacher as narrator of a subject and learners listening to memorize the narrated content, is something that we are all, to some extent, familiar with. But, as Freire (2009) argues, this teacher-centred approach must be rejected: '*they must abandon the educational goal of the deposit-making and replace it with the posing of the problems of human beings in their relations with the world*' (Freire, 2009 p. 79). Abandoning the banking concept and implementing the posing of problems is one of the backbones of problem based learning (PBL) and, hence, the problem-orientation and problem formations. Another pioneer in the field of 'posing of problems' was Howard Barrows, who in the late 1960s was involved in the early stages of the development of PBL at McMaster University in Canada. Barrow defined the concept in terms of specific characteristics as being student-centred, taking place in small groups with the teacher acting as a facilitator, and being organised around problems (de Graaff et. Kolmos, 2003, p. 657). In Denmark, the PBL model was developed based on ideas from, among others, Illeris, '*who formulated the principles of PBL as problem-oriented, project work, inter disciplinarily, participant directed learning and the exemplary principle and team work*' (Kolmos et al., 2004, p. 10).

At Aalborg University, all of the students and academic staff act out the basic principles of PBL, which is a general characteristic of all of the studies at the university. The principles, which are acknowledged by Aalborg University, are:

- Problem-orientation: Problems/wonderings appropriate to the study program serve as the basis for the learning process.
- Project organization: The project stands as both the means through which the students address the problem and the primary means by which students achieve the articulated educational objectives. The project is a multi-faceted and often extended sequence of tasks culminating in a final work product.
- Integration of theory and practice: The curriculum, instructional faculty members and project supervisors facilitate the process of connecting the specifics of project work to broader theoretical knowledge for the students. The students are able to see how theories and empirical/ practical knowledge interrelate.
- Participant direction: Students define the problem and make key decisions relevant to the successful completion of their project work.
- Team-based approach: A majority of the students' problem/project work is conducted in groups of three or more students.

- Collaboration and feedback: The students use peer and supervisor critique to improve their work. The skills of collaboration, feedback and reflection are an important outcome of the PBL model.

(Barge, 2010)

On the part-time Master's of Building Physics programme, which has been selected for this study, the PBL principles are well integrated into the study. The Master's of Building Physics is a research-based education programme that enrolls researchers and leading experts in the field, and which applies current scientific theories and methods to practical building-related issues.

This Master's is an accredited, qualifying continuing education programme, which is aimed at all professional groups with a long or intermediate higher education in the field of construction, such as:

- Civil, diploma and academics engineers;
- Building engineers; and,
- Architects.

In addition to a relevant higher education, it is required that the learner should have at least two years of practical experience at a high level of construction. This practical experience enables the learners to bring real-life problems with them into the Master's programme, which will be exemplified in Section 3.3.

2 RESEARCH APPROACH

The research approach in this study is basically a literature review of PBL, with a particular focus on problem formation, and a review of the Master's of Building Physics programme that has been selected as the subject context for this investigation. The literature review is expanded by empirical data that consists of problem formations, which are compiled among the Building Physics learners, demonstrating their ability to identify authentic problem formations within their everyday professional work and applying it as means for learning through their project work.

This paper will begin with a theoretical definition of problem formation in a PBL environment. It will then describe the Master's of Building Physics programme (curricula and semester description). Next, some examples of the student's problem formations will be given (i.e. research questions). This paper will then conclude with a discussion of the learners' opportunity and ability to draw real-life problems as a means for learning within the subject context of their study programme.

3 PROBLEM FORMATIONS IN PART-TIME MASTER'S PROGRAMMES

Aalborg University's pedagogical approach is solely based on the educational concept of PBL, which means that all of the students and staff enact the basic principles of PBL, including the part-time engineering Master's programmes. They

are designed according to the Aalborg PBL principles; that is, they are problem-based and project-organised. The learner's collaborate in teams, applying theory and practice to solve real-life engineering problems.

The use of problem formations as means for learning and problem-orientation is one of the pillars of the Aalborg PBL model. In relation to the Master's programmes, problem-orientation becomes even more applicable since the learner's are professionals with a working-life and practice, from where problems can be identified. From a learning perspective, the context of the problem has to be as authentic as possible. If the context is the learner's workplace, then the criteria for relevance must be met. Another observation that speaks for problem-orientation in continuing engineering education is the fact that '*53–88% of the participants in continuing educations are adults who are work-related motivated*' (Lorentsen et al. 2010). The learner's are work-motivated and this may support problem-orientation; hence, the learner experiences work-related qualifications and benefits.

3.1 Problem formations from a theoretical perspective

There have been many academic discussions about 'what is a problem'. Overall Kolmos (2004) argues that definitions of problems are diverse in different professional areas. Quist (2004) has, from a literature review of diverse problem formulations, located a variety of understandings. Basically, there is consensus that a problem can be initiated by a *wondering*, a *problematic situation* (Quist, 2004; Guerra & Bøgelund, 2014) or an *un-explored potential* (Guerra & Bøgelund, 2014 with reference to Borrows & Tamblyn, 1980; Quist 2004; Jonassen, 2011).

- A wondering: This indicates an observed phenomenon creating (qualified) curiosity (Quist, 2004), which can include situations, events, persons or a thing (Guerra & Bøgelund, 2014), something that happened or happens, something heard and seen (Quist, 2004), an uncovered need or wish (Guerra & Bøgelund, 2014; Quist, 2004).
- A problematic situation: This can, according to Quist (2004), be 'something you find a scandal', 'a lack of knowledge' or 'a lack of function' and it can be caused by contrasts; that is, between a wish and reality, conflicts, contradictions (Guerra & Bøgelund, 2014; Quist, 2004). In the definition of a problem, Guerra and Bøgelund (2014) explain the understanding of a problematic situation as also including the student's sorrow and/or indignation, frustration or stress, which makes them act to change this problematic situation.
- An un-explored potential. This idea is also a possible starting point for the problem formulation, such as the potential of a mobile phone not only as a device for communication but also to take photographs and video, agendas, e-mails, GPS applications and so forth.

Furthermore, consistent with the Aalborg PBL model, problem formations can be defined as theoretical, practical, social, technical, symbolic-cultural and/or scientific (Barge, 2010, p. 7). Depending on the type of problem and its starting point (a *wondering*, a *problematic situation* or an *un-explored potential*) there is also a distinction between 'retrospective' or 'prospective' problem formulations (Holgaard et.al. 2015, p. 37), which can be characterised by:

- Retro-spective problem formations want to find justifications and explanations for something already happened;
- Pro-spective problem formations are designed to solve practical problems and to produce concrete solutions

In summary, problem-orientation, or problem formations, as one of the basic principles of PBL, cannot be described and categorised as one and only type of problem. Problem-orientation is a concept that relates to various different types of problem formations with different points of departure, implementing distinctive theory and methods that are the means for solving the problem and which are documented by the learners in their project work.

3.2 The part-time Master's of Building Physics programme

The Master's of Building Physics programme has a background in two urgent challenges of social significance:

- More than a third of the total Danish energy consumption goes to the heating of buildings. To realise the goals set by the EU and the Danish government to reduce CO₂ emissions, it is imperative to significantly reduce the energy consumption of buildings.
- More than half of all building damage is caused by damp, such as in relation to energy efficiency and post-insulation. Many of the damages arise due to lack of knowledge or errors in design or execution. This results in an increased risk of damp accumulation, which may cause mould and poor indoor climate, and—in the longer term—degradation of materials and constructions.

Large energy savings in the construction industry can be difficult to achieve—both in building engineering, economic and cultural terms—and the damp-sensitive consequences result in additional complexity. In view of these challenges, there is a need for a competency lift among several professional groups in the building and property sector.

Building Physics Curriculum

Title: Master's dissertation of Building Physics
Module descriptions for the 4th semester

The Master's project is written within the building area and contains a presentation of previous research in the field and the Master's project relation to this.

Learning outcomes

Knowledge

The student must have obtained:

- In-depth knowledge of one or more selected subject elements.
- Wider insight into the field as regards theories and methods, as well as their mutual context, possibly in connection with a renovation or new-building project.

Skills

The student must have the following skills:

- Independently, systematically and critically identify, formulate and analyse the current problem formation.
- Relevantly relate the problem formation to the subject, including explaining and justifying the choices made in the delimitation of the problem formation.
- Relate the subject of the project to a historical context.

Competences

The student must have obtained the following competencies:

- Independently take and justify the choice of scientific, theoretical and/or experimental methods.
- Independently and critically evaluate the chosen theories and methods, as well as the project analyses, results and conclusions.
- Communicate relevant academic and professional aspects of project work in a clear and systematic way.

These are the goals for the learners and they should be followed throughout their Master's dissertation to demonstrate that they have achieved the defined learning outcomes, which is ranked in knowledge, skills and competences and which will be the basis for the assessment.

3.3 Cases

With a background in the two urgent challenges that have been identified (i.e. the need for energy savings and damp-sensitivity in construction), the learners have identified the following problem formations for their Master's dissertations.

Case 1: In-door damp insulation of an older brick-build basement: a case study and theoretical analysis of mineral insulation panels

How do the different types of insulation plates react to each other and does it matter what type of surface treatment is used?

Case 2: Bathrooms instead of back stairs: the conditions for establishing bathrooms in an existing back staircase

What are the damp conditions in a shared bathroom in a basement, bedroom with shower cabinet and existing back stairs?

Case 3: The thermal and atmospheric indoor climate in offices

What is the relationship between the measured and experienced thermal and atmospheric indoor climate in a number of offices in the City of Rødovre and the City of Copenhagen?

Case 4: Calculated energy versus measured energy consumption

How big is the energy requirement that is calculated in connection with the design of the building in relation to the energy used when the building is constructed and in operation?

Case 5: A study of the options for in-door climate and energy renovation in primary schools

This project examines whether or not there is a correlation between energy consumption (in terms of energy labels of the building) and the poor indoor climate in the public schools in Denmark?

On the basis of the problem formations, it is, of course, not possible to tell how well the learners have managed to meet all the learning outcomes outlined in the curriculum. However, it is possible to see if the problem formations are aligned with the topic of the semester and what type of problem formations the learners are able to come-up with.

4 DISCUSSION

This paper presents five different examples of Master's dissertation problem formations, which were randomly selected within the Master's of Building Physics programme. As the examples demonstrate, the learners identified innovative and real-life problems from their respective employment. Even though their backgrounds and jobs are very different, they all managed to draw up problem formations from their professional life, which also match the programme of study of the Master's of Building Physics.

The five problem formations were identified within the same study programme (curriculum) but they are diverse due to the different professional areas that the students worked in (Kolmos, 2004). The problem formations case 3 *'What is the relationship between the measured and experienced thermal and atmospheric indoor climate in a number of offices in the City of Rødovre and the City of Copenhagen?'* and case 4 *'How big is the energy requirement that is calculated in connection with the design of the building in relation to the energy used when the building is constructed and in operation?'* and case 5 *'This project examines whether or not there is a correlation between energy consumption (in terms of energy labels of the building) and the poor indoor climate in the public schools in Denmark?'* are all problem formations that can be identified as 'a wondering' since the learners explore phenomena which creates curiosity that can be disclosed. They can also be identified as retrospective projects because they seek justifications and explanations in regards to the phenomena. The problem formation case 1 *'How do the different types of insulation plates react to each other and does it matter what type of surface treatment is used?'* can be categorised as 'a problematic situation' because the project explores a lack of knowledge within different isolation plates and in their use. The problem formation is also designed to solve a practical problem, which is characterised as a prospective project. This is also the case for the problem formation case 2 *'What are the damp conditions in a shared bathroom in a basement, bedroom with shower cabinet and existing back stairs?'*, which produces a concrete solution to a practical problem. However, the problem formations can be identified as 'an un-explored potential' because the project explores the conditions for establishing bathrooms in a back staircase.

This analysis, of the five problem formations reveals their differences. Even when identified within the same curriculum, the diversity is clear. Nevertheless, they all are 'discipline projects' (Kolmos et al. 2008) because the method, discipline and subjects are given beforehand and the learners have chosen the subject within a rather narrow area of building physics.

Additionally, only one of the selected problem formations has been completed through group work (two learners). The other four have been completed by individual learners, which compared to Aalborg University's ordinary Master's students (MSc) is a high share of individualists. This might be due to the real-life problem formations: the learners are work-motivated and want to explore their 'own' professional practice and context.

The five selected problem formations reflect the learners' ability and shows that they are able to identify real-life problems within the frame of the Master's of Building Physics curriculum. However, the learners have identified diverse problems due to their different professional contexts and practice.

5 CONCLUSION

In this paper, the part-time Master's of Building Physics programme was presented as a case for the analysis to answer the question '*what types of problem formations are learners able to identify from their working-life. It will also ask if this is aligned with the requirements of the part-time Master's study programme.*' In conclusion, the analysis shows that the learners have ability and they are able to identify real-life problems within the frames of the Master's of Building Physics study programme. The problem formations are all aligned with the two overall identified topics of the semester: the need for energy savings and damp-sensitivity in construction. However, this rather narrowly identified topic leads to 'discipline projects' through which the problem formations are solved. When it comes to '*what type of problem formations the learners are able to identify*' this case shows that the five random selected problem formations are initiated by a wondering, a problematic situation and an un-explored potential. These three understandings of problems are represented in the case and they are retrospective and prospective perceptions of the problem formations. The diversity of the problem formations reflects the learners' work-related motivation because the problem formations are all initiated by their professional practice and context.

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Lifelong learning for the development of industrially oriented engineering skills: 4x4InSchools project

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ABSTRACT

Lifelong learning is a key factor for the development of a sustainable workforce. Recognized qualifications, such as engineering, alongside with transversal skills enhance individual employability. The authors aim to explore the rationale of one out-of-school and hands-on program, Project 4x4InSchools (4x4IS), as one of the pillars for the development of engineering and technical skills aiming to develop a positive vision of industrial and technical careers. The long-term objective is to raise awareness and knowledge of industry, industrial processes and its impact on everyday life towards industry and future engineering or technical career development. Namely careers in the metalworking sector or related industrial clusters. 4x4IS it's an international project with countries from five continents. This paper will focus on the Portuguese experience that encompasses youngsters from 15-18 years.

The lack of qualified industrial technicians and engineers, and consequently the lack of a qualified workforce has been on the agendas of governments worldwide. This issue gets more pronounced since Europe faces an aging workforce. This work rests on the belief that the promotion of technical and industrial skills is an important tool for vocational education and lifelong learning in consideration for sustainable development practises. The “new” industry must compete by adding value to industrial processes and products. These assets are made possible by innovative engineering and countries with innovation inputs related to human resources training and development (engineering education) directly linked with higher competitiveness standards. Thus,

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